

Teachers' Perceptions on Directors' Instructional Leadership in Secondary Resource Schools: Regional Variations and Impacts on Teachers Commitment in Cambodia

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Abstract

This research investigates instructional leadership (IL) in 12 secondary resource schools, comparing teachers' perceptions of their school directors' IL practices among three different regions and examining the effects of IL on teacher commitment to the school. A quantitative method was employed, with data gathered via a structured questionnaire from 619 teachers. One-way ANOVA analysis showed significant regional differences in teachers' perceptions of their school directors' ability to create school missions. However, there were no significant regional differences in teachers' perceptions of their school directors' effectiveness in developing the school learning climate. The findings from regression analysis also revealed that both school missions and school learning climate were significant predictors of teacher commitment to school.

Keywords: *Instructional leadership, teacher perceptions, school mission, teacher commitment, regional differences.*

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Introduction

School leadership has a significant impact on several school outcomes (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2005), student academic achievement (Leithwood & Mascall, 2008; Robinson et al., 2008a), and teacher attitudinal outcomes including teacher engagement, job satisfaction, and commitment (Hoch et al., 2018). According to Hallinger et al. (1996), principals' influence over the learning environment at school has an indirect impact on the success of the school. School leadership affects teachers' motivations, abilities, work environment, and climate, which in turn affect student outcomes and performance (Pont et al., 2008). According to Dinh et al. (2014), there are three positive leadership styles: ethical, authentic, and servant leadership. These styles emphasize the importance of ethics and authenticity while putting followers' and the community's welfare first. They also seek to restore trust and integrity in leadership. Beyond task compliance, positive leadership styles emphasize leader behaviors and interpersonal dynamics that boost followers' confidence and produce positive results, such as encouraging followers to go above and beyond expectations, pro-social behaviors, and positive self-development (Hannah et al., 2014). Scholars have said that the new types of leadership—authentic, servant, and ethic leadership styles—are conceptually different from transformational leadership. However, the correlations between transformational leadership and the new types of leadership seem to be somewhat redundant (Hoch et al., 2018).

A wealth of empirical studies spanning four decades has demonstrated the impacts of principals' instructional leadership (IL) on teacher abilities and student accomplishment. Most contexts recommend that school leaders should become proficient in IL, a fundamental leadership technique (Hallinger, 2011a; Leithwood et al., 2017). Studies have demonstrated that IL outperforms transformational leadership and distributed leadership in enhancing teacher learning and student achievement (Day et al., 2016; Hallinger, 2011a). According to a meta-analysis by Robinson et al. (2008), IL had an average impact on student outcomes that was three to four times greater than transformational leadership. With more than 200 studies from various countries and cultures (Hallinger & Wang, 2015a), IL has dominated the field of educational leadership in Western countries for almost 40 years (Zheng et al., 2019). However, PIMRS has received less attention in China's social and cultural context (Wei et al., 2018) and in other Asian countries (Hallinger & Walker, 2017).

Focusing on instructional leadership is crucial for both student learning and instructors' professional development (Kaparou & Bush, 2015). Empirical research, such as Darling-Hammond & Richardson, (2009); Somprach et al. (2017), and Wei et al. (2018) has repeatedly confirmed the beneficial impacts of principal leadership on teacher professional learning and the growth of the teacher professional community. According to this growing body of research, teacher attitudes (such as efficacy and

commitment) that influence their desire to participate in professional development have a major mediating role in the "principal leadership effects on teacher learning (Hallinger et al., 2019a). A related body of research (Day et al., 2016; Lieberman & Pointer Mace, 2008) supports these significant findings by demonstrating how teacher learning contributes to school improvement and sustainable education change.

Research on instructional leadership, like that of other educational leadership topics, has come from decentralized or partially decentralized contexts in Western societies, where principals have a great deal of discretion over how to run and lead their schools (Drago-Severson & Pinto, 2006; Flores, 2004; Leithwood, 1992). Nonetheless, centralized educational institutions are still common in Eastern Europe, Asia, and Africa (Bush, 2014). The system's regulations constrain principals' authority and decision-making due to its high degree of centralization (Oplatka, 2004). Hierarchical limitations and higher administration's principalship orientation limit school principals' ability to enhance teaching and learning processes, preventing them from dedicating significant time to pedagogical activities (Kaparou & Bush, 2015).

Instructional Leadership Theory

Hallinger and Wang (2015) created the principal instructional management rating scale (PIMRS), a popular conceptual framework. It has three dimensions: (a) establishing the school's mission; (b) overseeing the teaching program; and (c) creating a supportive school learning environment. The dimension of creating the school mission includes two job functions: (a) formulating school goals and (b) conveying those goals. The degree to which principals pinpoint the areas in which the school needs to improve and create performance targets for those areas is known as framing school goals. The function of communicating school goals refers to the principal's methods of conveying the significance of the school's objectives to staff, parents, and students (Hallinger & Wang, 2015a).

Working closely with teachers in curricular and instruction-related areas is part of managing the instructional program dimension (Hallinger & Murphy, 1985). This dimension includes the following three job functions (a) monitoring student progress, (b) organizing the curriculum, and (c) overseeing and assessing instruction. The degree to which principals encourage activities that offer teachers instructional support, observe classroom instruction through unofficial visits, and match classroom practices with school objectives is known as supervising and evaluating instruction (Hallinger & Heck, 1998a; Hallinger & Lu, 2014a; Hallinger & Murphy, 1985). Curriculum coordination refers to the activities the principals implement that enable staff to collaborate on aligning the curriculum with standards and achievement exams. The degree to which principals use test results to define objectives, evaluate the curriculum, review instruction, and track students' progress toward school goals is known as the job function of monitoring student progress (Hallinger & Murphy, 1985).

The third dimension of PIMRS encompasses five job functions: (a) protecting instructional time; (b) promoting professional development; (c) maintaining high visibility; (d) providing incentives to teachers; and (e) providing learning incentives. These five job functions collectively refer to the principals' implementation of "clear, explicit standards embodying what the school expects from students; through the careful use of school time; and the selection and implementation of high-quality staff development programs" to foster a positive learning environment in the school (Hallinger & Murphy, 1985).

Depending on the situation, instructional leadership takes on several forms. Certain curriculum-coordination-related PIMRS scales were dropped by some societies. Although most principals have teaching credentials and use them for leadership positions, they rarely meddle in classroom operations (Rodrigues & Ávila De Lima, 2024). For example, Antoniou and Lu (2018) discovered that certain elements in the PIMRS were relevant and inappropriate for assessing instructional leadership in China. Many components of the principal's curriculum coordination are inappropriate for this educational system, as the MoEY strictly regulates the curriculum and principals have limited power to make changes or improvements. Hallinger and Walker (2017) found that principals generally have less authority over the curriculum of their schools when they studied five Asian societies: China, Taiwan, Malaysia, Singapore, and Vietnam. These societies constrain the instructional leadership role of curriculum coordination, as suggested by Hallinger and Murphy (1985). Similarly, the Cambodian educational system provides limited authority for school principals over the curriculum.

Participants offered several explanations for the apparent disappearance of the principal's supervision over the curriculum. Firstly, they don't have the time to regularly observe classroom instruction or study curriculum development. Second, it was challenging to implement these procedures due to instructor reluctance, according to the school's principal. Teachers often felt uncomfortable in the classroom, considering it their territory. Third, there is a perception that the school principal is not actively supervising the curriculum and lacks knowledge in the curricular area. Lastly, especially in large schools, the principal finds it extremely difficult to meet with individual teachers to discuss the progress of their students (Rodrigues & Ávila De Lima, 2024).

One of the most well-known and sustainable leadership approaches is instructional leadership, primarily because it correlates with and demonstrated influence on student and school results (Hallinger & Heck, 1996; Robinson et al., 2008b). Most of the extensive and comprehensive body of information regarding instructional leadership comes from the United States of America (Hallinger, 2011b; Hallinger & Murphy, 1985). Throughout the years, researchers from throughout the world have developed empirically grounded models of instructional leadership practice (Hallinger, 2011b; Hallinger & Murphy, 1985; Leithwood et al., 2010).

Teachers' Perceptions Towards Instructional Leadership

A study with teachers in 230 Iraqi primary schools found that both teachers and principals perceive school directors to be actively participating in all three aspects of instructional leadership. All three dimensions revealed that the principals' mean self-evaluations exceeded the teachers' mean ratings, despite both teachers' and principals' mean ratings being "high" (with an impact exceeding 4 on the five-point Likert scale) (Hosseingholizadeh et al., 2023a). Previous studies have documented this trend of superintendents' self-ratings being higher (Hallinger et al., 2019b; Hallinger & Wang, 2015a). The teacher data was used to evaluate the instructional leadership construct in this work because the divergent variation patterns across principals and teachers provide more support for the use of teacher-reported data (Kulophas & Hallinger, 2020). Teachers and principals perceived the defining school mission dimension of the three instructional leadership subscales as a comparably high rating ($M = 4.26$, $SD = 0.70$, and $M = 4.58$, $SD = 0.29$, respectively). From the viewpoint of the instructors, this outcome alludes to the principal's duty to clearly define and convey a school's learning orientation (Hosseingholizadeh et al., 2023b).

In general, teachers at the three Mara Junior Science Colleges in Pahang, Malaysia, have a positive opinion of the school directors' instructional leadership. The standard deviation of the school's goals is .54, while the mean is 4.19. In contrast, the standard deviation for managing the instructional program is .54, while the mean is 3.97. Next in line was the excellent school learning climate mean of 3.95 with a standard deviation of .55. This indicates that principals carry out their job as instructional leaders in all areas, with standard deviations almost equal (Ail et al., 2015).

Organizational Commitment

The definition of teacher commitment to school expects highly dedicated teachers to support the school's objectives, exceed expectations, and remain employed by the school (Abd Razak et al., 2010). Compared to other aspects of teacher commitment, teacher commitment to school has been the subject of more thorough definitions, assessments, and studies (Reichers, 1985; Yousef, 2000). Many scholars have examined the nature and impact of teacher commitment to school (e.g., Kushman, 1992; Somech & Bogler, 2002). Compared to high school instructors, elementary school teachers exhibit noticeably higher levels of organizational commitment, according to these writers. Teachers who are highly committed to their school strive to meet school objectives, exceed expectations, and remain loyal to the school. This study found that teachers' commitment to the school is based on their belief and acceptance of its goals and values, their efforts to achieve them, and their strong desire to be involved. Mowday et al. (1979) used three factors to explain the concept of organizational commitment: a strong desire to retain members of the organization, a strong belief in and approval of the organization's goals and values, and an eagerness to put forth extraordinary effort for the organization's benefit.

Teachers' Perceptions of Commitment to School

A study in Malaysian primary schools found that culture influences teacher commitment. It claimed that in-school working conditions had greatly direct effects on teacher commitment and cultural orientation also directly influenced teacher commitment (Abd Razak et al., 2010). In addition to this, other findings found that there were significant mean differences in teacher commitment to school between Malay and Indian, and between Chinese and Indian teachers at a significance level of 0.05. However, there were no significant mean differences found between Malay and Chinese teachers. For commitment to students, there were significant mean differences between Chinese and Malaysian teachers, and between Chinese and Indian teachers, but not between Malay and Indian teachers. Concerning commitment to teaching, there were significant mean differences found between Malay and Indian teachers, and between Chinese and Indian teachers. Meanwhile, there were no significant mean differences between Chinese and Malay teachers (Thien & Razak, 2014).

The Impacts of IL on Teacher Commitment to School

The relationships between principal leadership and teacher commitment have been the subject of extensive research (Geijsel et al., 2003; Hallinger & Lu, 2014a; Marshal, 2015). This body of research suggests that a variety of leadership styles, such as distributed, transformational, and instructional leadership, can positively impact teacher commitment to school (Hallinger & Lu, 2014a; Marshal, 2015). This larger study's results demonstrated a positive correlation between principal instructional leadership and teacher commitment. For instance, a study in Istanbul found that instructional leadership significantly influenced teacher commitment to school

(Cansoy et al., 2022; Sarikaya & Erdogan, 2016). Similar research suggests that instructional leadership influences teacher commitment (Al-Mahdy et al., 2018; Hallinger et al., 2018; Hallinger & Lu, 2014a). Researchers have discovered a direct correlation between teacher affective commitment and instructional leadership.

In particular, instructional leadership has a crucial role in encouraging instructors to become more dedicated to their work, which enhances student learning outcomes (Sun, 2015). Good instructional leadership may boost teachers' commitment to their work and readiness to invest in the overall growth of the school (Hallinger & Heck, 1998b). Additionally, principals can encourage teachers' dedication to their profession by establishing school objectives and tasks, enhancing teacher performance, resolving issues in the teaching process, and improving the learning environment in the school (Hallinger, 2018)

Materials and Methods

Research Objectives

There are two main objectives of the present research as follow:

1. To examine if there are any significant differences concerning teachers' perceptions of principal instructional leadership from different regions.
2. To investigate the relationship between instructional leadership and teacher commitment to school.

Research Design

This quantitative research employs two research designs- causal-comparative and correlational research designs. One-way ANOVA was used to examine the mean differences in teachers' perceptions of instructional leadership in different regions. Pearson correlation is used to investigate the correlation between the subscale of IL and teacher commitment to school, and multiple regression is used to investigate the effects of sub-constructs of IL on teacher commitment to school.

Measures

The measures of Instructional leadership were adapted from the PIMRS Teacher Short Forms with 22 items (Hallinger & Wang, 2015b). Our measures of IL comprised two sub-constructs of IL – school mission and school learning climate with 11 items. Each statement is rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from (1) almost never to (5) almost always. Managing instructional programs was excluded because in some Asian countries such as China, Taiwan, Malaysia, Singapore, and Vietnam, principals typically have less control in creating their school's curriculum (Hallinger & Walker, 2017), and in Cambodia's education system, principals have limited authority to manage the curriculum. Teacher commitment to school was measured by seven items adapted from (Mowday et al., 1979b). The teachers rated the statements on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree.

Population and Samples

The study's participants are secondary resource school teachers who have access to computer laboratories, libraries, science laboratories, meeting rooms, and a teachers' lounge. By giving students, the chance to participate in experiments and hands-on projects that connect classroom concepts to real-world applications, secondary resource schools have been especially significant in advancing STEM education. There

are currently 50 secondary resource schools throughout Cambodia (Un et al., 2021). According to RGC (2020), there are four regions: Central Plain, Tonle Sap, Plateau and Mountain, and Coastal and Sea. Firstly, the researcher selected three regions using simple random selection. The researcher then chose two provinces at random from each region, followed by two resource schools from each province. Thus, the study selected twelve resource schools and six provinces. Of the 1465 teachers (563 females) from the target schools, 619 teachers—or 42.25% of the total population—participated in the current study. There are 180 teachers from four secondary resource schools combined in the Tonle Sap region, 253 from four schools in the Central Plain region, and 186 from four additional schools in the Coastal and Sea zone.

Table 1. Participants' Demographic Information

Variables	Responses	Number	Percentage
Types of Regions	Teachers from schools in Tole Sap	180	29.1%
	Teachers from schools in Central Plain	253	40.9%
	Teachers from schools in Coastal and Sea	186	30.0%
Gender	Male	356	57.50%
	Female	263	42.50%
Age range	25 years or below	11	1.80%
	26-35 years	103	16.60%
	36-45 years	267	43.10%
	Above 46 years	238	38.40%
Level of education	Baccalaureate	125	20.20%
	Associate Degree	22	3.60%
	Bachelor's degree	388	62.70%
	Master	84	13.60%
Teaching experience	1-5 years	27	4.40%
	6-10 years	70	11.30%
	11-15 years	91	14.7%
	16-20 years	113	18.30%
	21- Over	318	51.40%

Results

Descriptive Statistics for IL Perceived by Teachers (n = 619)

The means and standard deviation along with reliability statistics for research variables are displayed in Table 2. Teachers reported relatively high perceptions of instructional leadership ($M = 4.21$, $SD = 0.59$) with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.91 and of their commitment to school ($M = 4.38$, $SD = 0.49$) with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.92. For each sub-construct of instructional leadership, teachers also reported relatively high perceptions. In particular, teachers' perceptions of the school mission ($M = 4.25$, $SD = 0.56$), with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.87, while teachers' perceptions of the school learning climate were also high ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 0.71$) with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.88.

Table 2. Teacher Perceptions of IL and Teacher Commitment to School

Variables	N	Mean	SD	α	Skewness	Kurtosis
Instructional Leadership	619	4.21	.59	0.91		
School Mission	619	4.25	.56	0.87	-.85	1.54
Positive school learning climate	619	4.00	.71	0.88	-.69	.45
Commitment to school	619	4.38	.49	0.92	-.52	.78

Note: α is Cronbach's alpha.

Multiple Comparisons of IL and Commitment to School

Table 3. Mean and SD Various Tests regarding the Teachers' Perceptions of the Research Variables

Perceived variables	Schools in the Tole Sap Region		Schools in Central Plain		Schools in Coastal and Sea Region		F
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
School Mission	4.27	.56	4.15	.58	4.37	.49	***8.374
Positive school learning climate	4.00	.76	3.94	.71	4.10	.66	2.402
Commitment to school	4.38	.52	4.28	.46	4.51	.47	***11.678

Notes: Perceptions of instructional leadership (school mission, and positive school learning climate) and teacher commitment to school in the three types of regions. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.001$; *** $p < 0.0001$

One of the primary purposes of this study is to investigate regional differences in teachers' perceptions of their school directors' instructional leadership including their perceptions of the school mission, school learning climate, and self-reported commitment to school in three types of regions: Tonle Sap, Central Plain, and Coastal and Sea. One-way ANOVA was employed to test these differences, with the findings shown in Table 3.

Multiple Comparisons for Creating School Mission

The results in Tables 3 and 4 displayed that there are significant differences in the teachers' perceptions of creating school missions between different regions in which schools are located ($F(2, 616) = 8.374, p < 0.0001$). A post hoc Bonferroni test in Table 4 revealed that teachers in the Coastal and Sea regions rated their principals' ability to create a school mission higher than those in the Central Plain region. However, Teachers' perceptions of the school mission in Tonle Sap were not different from those in both the Central Plain and Coastal and Sea regions.

Table 4. Multiple Comparisons for Creating School Mission

(I) Region	(J) Region	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Tole Sap	Central Plain	.11980	.05369	.078	-.0091	.2487
	Coastal and Sea	-.09559	.05757	.292	-.2338	.0426
Central Plain	Tolesap	-.11980	.05369	.078	-.2487	.0091
	Coastal and Sea	-.21539*	.05318	.000	-.3431	-.0877
Coastal and Sea	Tolesap	.09559	.05757	.292	-.0426	.2338
	Central Plain	.21539*	.05318	.000	.0877	.3431

Note: * The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Multiple Comparisons for Teachers' Perceptions of School Learning Climate

Table 3 and Table 5 displayed no significant differences in teachers' perceptions of the school learning climate across the Central Plain, Coastal and Sea, and Tonle Sap regions $F(2,616) = 2.402, p > .05$. In this sense, teachers in the three regions provided the similar levels of school learning climate implemented by principals.

Table 5. Multiple Comparisons of School Learning Climate

(I) Region	(J) Region	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Tolesap	Central Plain	.04951	.06905	1.000	-.1162	.2153
	Coastal and Sea	-.09967	.07404	.536	-.2774	.0781
Central Plain	Tolesap	-.04951	.06905	1.000	-.2153	.1162
	Coastal and Sea	-.14918	.06840	.089	-.3134	.0150
Coastal and Sea	Tolesap	.09967	.07404	.536	-.0781	.2774
	Central Plain	.14918	.06840	.089	-.0150	.3134

Multiple Comparisons for Teachers' Self-Reported Commitment to School

The findings in Table 3 displayed that Levene's Test for homogeneity of variances yielded $F(2, 616) = 11.678, p = 0.40$. This indicated a violation of the assumption of equal variances in the regions for teacher commitment to the school. Therefore, the Games-Howell post hoc test was appropriately used to compare the differences between regions when variances and sample size were unequal (Field, 2013; Games & Howell, 1976).

Table 6. Multiple Comparisons for Teachers' Self-Reported Commitment

(I) Region	(J) Region	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Tole Sap	Central Plain	.09319	.04841	.133	-.0207	.2071
	Coastal and Sea	-.13144*	.05170	.031	-.2531	-.0098
Central Plain	Tole Sap	-.09319	.04841	.133	-.2071	.0207
	Coastal and Sea	-.22463*	.04498	.000	-.3304	-.1188
Coastal and Sea	Tole Sap	.13144*	.05170	.031	.0098	.2531
	Central Plain	.22463*	.04498	.000	.1188	.3304

Note: *. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The Game-Howell post hoc test in Table 6 displayed significant differences in the perceptions of commitment to schools across different regions. The finding showed that teachers in the Coastal and Sea regions had the highest commitment, which was significantly higher than those in both Tonle Sap and Central Plain regions. However, there were no significant differences were found in teacher commitment between the Tonle Sap and Central Plain regions.

Correlation between Sub-Constructs and Sub-Constructs

Table 7. Correlation Between Sub-Construct and Sub-Construct

Variables	1	2	3
1. School Mission	-		
2. Positive School Learning Climate	.66**	-	
3. Organizational Commitment	.49**	.47**	-

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The sub-construct of instructional leadership- creating school mission, and school learning climate was significantly and positively correlated with teacher commitment to school as shown in Table 7. Teachers' perceptions of creating a school mission implemented by the principal were significantly correlated with teacher commitment to school ($r = 0.49, p < 0.001$), and teachers' perceptions were also found positively and significantly correlated with teacher commitment to school ($r = 0.47, p < 0.001$).

The Effects of Instructional Leadership and Teacher Commitment to School

Table 8. Predictors of Teacher Commitment to School

Variables	B	SE	β	R ²	Sig.	df	F	Semi-Partial
Model	2.48	.13		.276	.000	2	118.52	
School Mission	.28	.04	.31		.000			.267
Positive school learning climate	.18	.03	.26		.000			.226

Not: R² = Adjusted R-Square

Simultaneous multiple regression was employed to examine the best predictors of teacher commitment to school. The mean, standard deviation, and inter-correlations are displayed in Table 2 and Table 7. The combination of variables to predict teacher commitment to school from sub-constructs of instructional leadership namely creating school mission and school learning climate was statistically significant $F(2, 616) = 118.52, p < .0001$). The beta coefficients are shown in Table 8. Note that gender, teaching experiences, and education of the respondents are not included as predictors of teacher commitment to school. The adjusted R² value was 0.276. This indicates that 27.6% of the variance in teacher commitment to school was explained by the model. Both school mission ($\beta = .31, p < .0001$) and school learning climate ($\beta = .26, p < .0001$) were significant predictors of teacher commitment to the school.

Discussion

The first purpose of this study was to investigate the differences in teachers' perceptions of their principals' instructional leadership and their commitment to school. The findings of the present research showed that teachers generally rated high perceptions of their principals' instructional leadership and their commitment to the school. In particular, teachers had high perceptions of the school's mission and the school's learning climate. However, there were significant regional differences found

in certain areas. Teachers in the Coastal and Sea region rated significantly higher on how well their school directors were able to create school missions compared to those in the Central Plain region. Interestingly, there were no significant differences found in teachers' perceptions concerning school learning climate in the three regions. Finally, there were significant differences found in teachers' commitment to school. Teachers in the Coastal and Sea regions showed the highest levels of commitment to school.

The present findings were first in line with previous studies indicating that teachers generally had high perceptions of their principals' instructional leadership. For example, a study in Iraqi primary schools found that teachers and principals rated three dimensions of IL relatively high (Hosseingholizadeh et al., 2023a). Similarly, the findings of the present study were also consistent with those of Ail et al. (2015), who found that teachers in Malaysia have a high perception of principals' effectiveness in creating a school learning climate and school mission.

However, the present findings were in contrast to those of Bellibas et al. (2016), who found that teachers in 23 primary schools in Turkey perceived their principals' instructional leadership as quite low. Particularly, Turkish teachers rated school mission ($M = 3.16$), managing instructional leadership ($M = 2.95$), and developing school learning climate ($M = 3.28$). The results suggest that Turkish primary school principals are generally not strong in their instructional leadership skills (Gümüő & Akcaoglu, 2013).

Secondly, the present results are consistent with previous findings that claimed how cultural and contextual factors can impact teacher commitment to school. For example, a study in Malaysian primary schools by (Abd Razak et al., 2010) Abd Razak et al. (2010) indicated that cultural orientation and in-school working conditions had direct impacts on teacher commitment. Similarly, Thien and Razak (2014) found significant differences in teacher commitment across ethnic groups in Malaysia.

The second purpose is to investigate the relationship between instructional leadership and teacher commitment to school. The present findings showed that both school mission and school learning climate were significant predictors of teacher commitment to school. The current findings were supported by previous researchers who found that instructional leadership significantly influences teacher commitment (Al-Mahdy et al., 2018; Hallinger et al., 2018; Hallinger & Lu, 2014b).

Conclusion

The findings of the present research highlighted some profound insights concerning teachers' perceptions of their principals' instructional leadership and its effects on teacher commitment to school. First, it found that there were significant regional differences in teachers' perceptions of their school directors' ability to create a school mission. Teachers in the Coastal and Sea regions rated this sub-construct higher than those in the Central Plain region. However, there were no significant differences between schools in Tonle Sap and those in the other regions. Second, there were no significant differences between teachers' perceptions of their principals' developing school learning climate.

Finally, multiple regression analysis displayed that both school missions and learning climate were significant predictors of teacher commitment to school. The model explained 27.6% of the variances in teacher commitment to school. Both creating a

school mission and developing a school climate are strong predictors of the teachers' commitment to the school.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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